

SNSPD-Assisted Φ -OTDR for Zero-Touch Deployment of Amplifier-Free Distributed Acousto-Optic Sensing in PONs

Bernhard Schrenk, and Florian Honz

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Center for Digital Safety & Security / Security & Communication Technologies, 1210 Vienna, Austria.
 Author e-mail address: bernhard.schrenk@ait.ac.at

Abstract: We employ a high-sensitivity Geiger-mode detector to overcome power-splitting loss in PONs, demonstrating the acquisition of a drop-side acousto-optic signature behind a 1:32 power-splitter through a centralized DAS interrogator – without optical amplifier.

1. Introduction

Distributed fiber-optic sensing is gaining interest due to the versatile applications it can serve. Phase-sensitive approaches that capture and localize disturbances through mechanical vibrations imprinted on optical phase changes have been shown. Examples include the identification of tampering attempts, pinpointing of leakage along critical energy infrastructures [1], or city-wide urban activity tracking [2]. Broadband access deployment bears an enormous potential toward a pervasive use of fiber-optic sensing. However, practical implementations for distributed acousto-optic sensing (DAS) mostly aim at point-to-point fiber links that are dedicated to high-value assets, while point-to-multipoint passive optical access networks (PON) are characterized by a split-based architecture that features a high loss for its signal distributing element. Earlier works have addressed this challenge by incorporating fiber Bragg gratings (1:4 split PON) [3], through use of concentrated UPC connector joints as sensing points (1:4 split) [4], or through enhanced-scattering fiber along the drop segment to offset a 1:16 split loss by the ~ 20 dB increased backscattering [5]. Alternatively, active optical mirrors at the optical network terminals (ONT) [6] or simplified field-distributed interrogators at the ONTs [7] can be applied. Nonetheless, all these approaches depend on physical-layer modifications of the fiber plant or ONTs, which are often seen as road-blocks for practical PON deployments.

In this work we capitalize on centralized detector assets to mitigate the need to modify the optical distribution network (ODN). Following a composable approach for centralized DAS, we employ a single-photon detector in an amplifier-less interrogator to facilitate the acquisition of a vibration phase behind a 1:32 split in a zero-touch short-reach PON configuration. We further discuss the limitations when employing Geiger-mode single-photon detection.

2. Composable High-Sensitivity DAS Interrogator with Centralized Single-Photon Receiver

This investigation shall consider a heterogeneous access/x-haul architecture (Fig. 1a), which apart from optical communication further integrates fiber sensing and quantum key distribution (QKD) as additional network assets. This setting aims to off-load complexity to the edge cloud and pools equipment such as quantum receivers, building on the unidirectional nature of QKD links [8]. A case in point for this integration methodology are super-conducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPD) [9], which – despite their excellent detection efficiency – are considered as too complex for tail-end network units. Here, we employ such an SNSPD in an interferometric DAS receiver. Since QKD links do not require continuous operation due to demand-specific key consumption and key buffering, SNSPD elements within a centralized detector pool

Fig. 1. (a) DAS interrogator with quantum receiver. (b) Experimental setup. (c) Optical budget for SNSPD (S) and APD (A)-based interrogators.

Fig. 2. (a) Example for SNSPD signal. (b) Acquired vibration phase after signal reconstruction. (c) Corresponding spectrum and (d) SNR.

can be temporarily re-connected to a co-located DAS system to gain a high-sensitivity receiver for on-demand probing.

3. Experimental Setup and Power Budget for DAS-Based Fiber Sensing

The setup to investigate the proposed DAS system is presented in Fig. 1b. We employed a narrow-linewidth laser (NLL) whose launch at 10 mW operates at 1550.12 nm, with a linewidth of 100 Hz. An acousto-optic modulator (AOM) is employed to carve 100-ns probe pulses at a repetition rate of $f_F = 80$ kHz, which is adjusted to the short-reach fiber plant (FP1) that initially consists of a straight p2p link with two 100-m single-mode fiber (SMF) spools L_1, L_2 . In between these, the fiber is exposed to a loudspeaker that emits an acoustic tone Φ at 200 Hz. The return signal caused by Rayleigh backscattering is the received by the DAS interrogator, for which two implementations are investigated: The proposed SNSPD-based DAS receiver (S) for an amplifier-free interrogator consists of a combination of fiber couplers as interferometric demodulator, following a 3×3 layout as 120° hybrid [10]. The demodulated signal is connected to a SNSPD detector with a detection efficiency of 93%, a dark-count rate of 16 cts/s and a dead-time of ~ 33 ns. We had to introduce additional attenuation (VOA) to avoid saturation of the SNSPD, even though no single EDFA has been used in this DAS configuration. Moreover, since only one SNSPD was available, we can only acquire one of the three demodulator outputs. This limitation is avoided in the second DAS configuration (A), which employs three APD+TIA detectors at the 120° hybrid. Yet, this APD-based receiver requires the use of two filtered EDFAs to overcome power budget limitations, located at the transmitter and as preamplifier for the receiver. The detected signals are acquired by a real-time oscilloscope and we performed start-of-frame detection and an extraction of the frame-to-frame phase to yield the induced vibration along the fiber link.

The power budget for both DAS interrogator schemes is discussed in Fig. 1c in terms of average signal power. The SNSPD-enabled DAS interrogator (S) features a massive optical budget of 113 dB between NLL launch and its saturation level, which allows us to acquire the return signal in an amplifier-less fashion. For the FP1 ODN configuration, the VOA before the SNSPD had to be set to add ~ 27 dB of extra attenuation to avoid saturation. This attenuation can be eroded by ODN loss, for example through a (bidirectionally passed) split. In contrary, the APD-based interrogator (A) requires the use of two EDFAs to remain above the sensitivity limit of its photodetectors.

4. Signal Recovery for Reception with SNSPD-based DAS Interrogator

Figure 2a shows an example for a signal trace at the SNSPD output when operated at a signal feed equivalent to 250 kcts/s. Binary pulses originate at the begin of each frame as events linked to the return signal along the fiber

Fig. 3. (a) Reach-resolved phase acquired by SNSPD-based receiver and (b) time-distance map, making comparison to the APD-based receiver.

Fig. 4. (a) Acquisition of drop-side vibration phase Φ after various power splitters, and (b) for the reach scale of p2p mobile fronthaul links.

spans. The sparsity in detection events prevents a one-shot signal acquisition. For this reason, we accumulate events over multiple frames to reconstruct the analog return signal. Figure 2b shows this reconstruction for various aggregation times τ_A , which together with the repetition period $\tau_F = 1/f_F = 12.5 \mu\text{s}$ corresponds to a number of applied frames N_F . We see that after 20 frames (\blacklozenge) the reach-resolved signature of Φ shows a contrast ζ of 10.6 dB towards the background (Fig. 3a). At this point, a clean 200-Hz tone (\bullet) is yielded in the low-frequency spectrum (Fig. 2c). Further accumulation raises the SNR σ of this tone up to a point where τ_A approaches the period of Φ . This is evident for the faded signal at $N_F = 350$ (\blacktriangledown) or $\tau_A = 4.38$ ms, which falls close to the signature's period of 5 ms. This fading is also resembled in Fig. 3d, which summarizes the SNR σ for the Φ -induced tone as a function of τ_A .

5. Performance Evaluation: SNSPD- vs. APD-based DAS Interrogator and Impact of Power-Splitting ODN

Figure 3a reports the reach-resolved vibration phase acquired through the SNSPD-based DAS interrogator (**S**) after performing several DSP steps. Results for the normalized phase φ_n are presented along various (color-coded) acquisition frames to indicate the time-dependence of the detected vibration phase. The total link reach L_{tot} that includes both SMF spools and several patchcords, and the phase excursion due to the signature Φ at 120 m can be clearly discerned, which prove the good acquisition quality of the SNSPD receiver. A corresponding time-distance intensity map of the acquired vibration phase is presented in Fig. 3b. The 200-Hz tone of Φ is clearly enhanced toward the background noise and allows for a correct identification. Though not guaranteeing long-term performance, the low NLL linewidth ensures that no fast fading is present, even though only one of the three ports of the 120° hybrid have been acquired by the SNSPD-based DAS interrogator. For comparison, the EDFA+APD-based DAS interrogator (Fig. 3b, **A**) yields a reach-resolved signature of Φ with a contrast ζ of 20.5 dB. Yet, there is no reception possible once introducing a power split between L_1 and L_2 , despite the use of two EDFAs.

We therefore investigated the capability of the SNSPD-enabled DAS interrogator to capture a signature Φ behind a power splitter. For this, we used fiber plant **FP2** (Fig. 1b) with a $1:N$ split. The vibration phase is then introduced between L_2 and L_3 . Figure 4a presents the time-distance maps for $L_1 = L_2 = L_3 = 100$ m. Since the return signals arising behind the splitter are attenuated by N^2 , we replaced the VOA before the SNSPD by a fast optical 1×1 switch (BATI Nanona) to dynamically blank the return signal generated along the first span L_1 through an on-off gating ratio of 26 dB. This ensures single-photon detector operation without entering deep saturation. The signature Φ can then be clearly acquired for a split ratio up to $1:16$, for which the SNR with respect to post-split return signals along L_2+L_3 is 11.2 dB. When increasing the split further, the contrast ζ starts to drop as the input to the SNSPD due to signals arising past the splitter falls well below its saturation level. Yet, for a $1:32$ split, ζ remains as high as 8.6 dB.

We finally acquired a vibration phase Φ of 100 Hz for a longer fiber reach of $L_1 = 14.6$ km, which leads to a lower repetition rate f_F of 5 kHz and thus limits the parameter N_F used for signal recovery. Figure 4b shows a corresponding acquisition. The longer reach results in continuous SNSPD detection events over a longer time span, thus limiting the number detection events that are directly attributed to Φ before reaching SNSPD saturation. Still, the signature Φ can be clearly acquired at an SNR of 8.6 dB ($N_F = 20$), without requiring additional optical gating.

6. Conclusion

We have proposed and demonstrated the use of a SNSPD in a centralized DAS interrogator to overcome the power-splitting loss in PON deployments. The remarkable sensitivity of the SNSPD enabled us to acquire an acousto-optic signature behind the $1:32$ split of an urban short-reach PON configuration, even without employing a single EDFA. The Geiger-mode operation of the SNSPD complicates the use in long-reach fiber plants since an acquisition over multiple frames is a necessity to reconstruct the phase profile. A fully-furnished 3×3 SNSPD

demodulator and the pinpointing of simultaneously detected events at multiple PON branches are left for future investigation.

Acknowledgement: This work has received funding from the EU Horizon Europe R&I programme (GA 101113901).

7. References

- [1] M. Jia et al., "Pipeline Leaks Early Warning Based on Distributed Optical Fiber Sensing Technology," *PTL* **36**, 397 (2024)
- [2] J. Liu et al., "Urban sensing using existing fiber-optic networks," *Nat. Comm.* **16**, 3091 (2025)
- [3] F. Sandah et al., "Monitoring of FTTH-PON using direct-detection FBG-assisted ϕ -OTDR," *Proc. OFS*, Tu6.55 (2025)
- [4] M. Liu et al., "Enhanced Multi-Branch Sensing by Leveraging the Fresnel reflection points in ϕ -OTDR-based...", *Proc. OFS*, Tu6.9 (2025)
- [5] B. Zhu et al., "Distributed Acoustic Sensing Over PON Architecture by Using Enhanced Scattering Fiber," *JLT* **43**, 6285 (2025)
- [6] Y. Huang et al., "Simultaneous Optical Fiber Sensing and Mobile Front-Haul Access over a Passive Optical...", *Proc. OFC'20*, Th1K4 (2020)
- [7] B. Schrenk et al., "Field-Distributed Φ -OTDR Through Dissemination of Narrow-Linewidth Light and Optically Synchronized Proxy Sources," *Proc. ECOC*, M.03.08.1 (2025)
- [8] N. Vokic et al., "Differential Phase-Shift QKD in a 2:16-Split Lit PON with 19 Carrier-Grade Channels", *JSTQE* **26**, 6400309 (2020)
- [9] L Stasi et al., "Enhanced Detection Rate and High Photon-Number Efficiencies with a Scalable Parallel SNSPD," *ACS Phot.* **12**, 320 (2025)
- [10] D. Brown et al., "A symmetric 3x3 coupler based demodulator for fiber optic interferometric sensors," *Proc. SPIE* **1584**, 328 (1991)